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A Study of Self Regulated Learning of Secondary School Students with reference to Gender and Academic Achievement

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Abstract

The present research was an attempt to study self-regulated learning of secondary school students with reference to gender and academic achievement. All secondary school students who study in the Bulandshahr district rural areas schools of UP Board are selected as this research population. Random Sampling technique was using by researcher for selecting the sample. Firstly, researcher was prepared a list of schools of Bulandshahr district. Lottery technique was used by selection of rural areas schools randomly. Total 120 students from secondary school were selected as sample for this research. In order to accomplish the objectives of the present research, the researcher had been used the Descriptive Survey method for the study. The results showed that the self-regulation has an impact on academic achievement of secondary school students. In this study, gender is not affect on Self Regulated learning.

Introduction

Self-regulation is the ability to understand and manage students own behavior and reactions to feeling and think happening around them. Self-regulation is a task that helps student reach metacognition which plays an important role in deep understanding.

Self-regulation is a self-directive process. It is helping a student transform her/ his cognitive ability into academic skills. Learning is like an activity which is effect by teaching (Zimmerman, 2001). Zimmerman and Schunk (1989) define self-regulated learning is a systematic learning. This type learning is helpful for students' self-developed thoughts, feelings, or actions and achievement of their own goals. Berk (2003) also explains that Self-regulation is a process which is helping a person continuously monitoring the progress of her/his goal, outcomes, and rechanneling the unsuccessful attempt.

Student's cognition, behaviour, emotions and motivation are control by self-regulation. It is a ways to achieve their establish goals (Panadero & Alonso-Tapia, 2014). Corsi (2010) viewed self-regulated learning is like a system. It is cultivate the higher thinking skills in students by their innate strengths. It is help to finding a good solution of student's problems using their natural qualities and abilities. This type of learning techniques permission the students to learn and manipulate their environment by

using their different learning method to interact with it. According to Winnie and Perry (2006), self-regulated students are aware to their weaknesses and strengths of academic performance. Self-regulation is also helpful selection of suitable strategies for every day challenges of a student's academic works. Therefore, self-regulation is a way which is help to achieve student systematic learning. Systematic learning is help to achieve student's learning goals freely.

Dimensions of Self-Regulated Learning: After an extensive survey of available literature in the concerned area, the functional concepts of following six self-regulated learning dimensions were adapted for quantitative measure:

- (a) **Self-Awareness:** Self-awareness is an individual's capacity to notice the self. It is a key to realize one's own strengths and weaknesses.
- (b) **Planning and Goal Setting:** Planning involves thinking, analysing, organizing the activities and allocating resources that are required to achieve a desired goal.
- (c) **Self-Motivation:** Self-Motivation involves action to undertake or carry on a work or activity without another's prodding or supervision.
- (d) **Self-Control:** Self-control is essential to regulating learner's behaviour. It is a cognitive process.

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- (e) **Self-Evaluation:** Self-evaluation involves the evaluation of the effectiveness of learning strategies as well as of study skills used.
- (f) **Self-Modification:** Self-modification involves various kinds of reactions and reflections on the self and the task or context. It helps in replacing undesirable behaviour with more desirable behaviour.

Actively increase the level of motivation, meta-cognition and behaviour by academic self-regulation. The academic self-regulation is like a level. It is help to active learning process and achieving the goal. The academic self-regulation is a degree to which students are motivationally, meta-cognitively and behaviorally active in their learning process and in accomplishing their goals (Zimmerman, 2000). According to Pintrich (2003) research, she is being sure that self regulation is help the students achieve to set goals. Monitoring, management and control of cognition are parts of self regulation. All of these are improve the learner's motivational behavior and environment. It is indeed that learners are actively improve participants of their own learning. The academic achievement of physics performance of learners can improve by the Self-regulation learning (Achufusi-Aka & Offiah, 2010). They found that self regulated learning and academic achievement is a strong relationship with undergraduate students (N.A. Bakar, A. Shuaibu, R. Abu Bakar, 2017). Hong Kong student's self-regulated learning is directly related to academic performance like reading, mathematics problems and science aspect (Esther Sui-Chu Ho, 2003). The study of above researches we could be findings that self-regulation is a very importance role for students's learning process.

The present study aims to study Self-Regulated Learning and the impact of self-regulation on academic achievement of secondary school students in Rural Area of Bulandshahr.

Objectives of The Study

In this research, researcher was worked with the

following objectives:

1. To study the self-regulation of secondary school students.
2. To compare the self-regulation of girls and boys students studying in secondary classes.
3. To find out the impact of self-regulation on academic achievement of secondary school students.

Hypotheses

H₁: There is no significant difference between the self-regulation of girls and boys students studying in classes.

H₂: There is no significant impact of self-regulation on academic achievement of secondary school students.

Research Design

All IXth class students who study in the Bulandshahr district rural areas schools of UP Board are selected as this research population. Random Sampling technique was using by researcher for selecting the sample. Firstly, researcher was prepared a list of schools of Bulandshahr district. Lottery technique was used by selection of rural areas schools randomly. Total 120 students from Class IX were selected as sample for this research. In order to accomplish the objectives of the present investigation, the researcher had been used the Descriptive Survey method for the study.

In this study researcher was used to measure self-regulation by Dr. Madhu Gupta & Ms. Dimple Mehtani's Self-Regulated Learning Scale and Ms. Dimple Mehtani and final achievement tests scores were considered for academic achievement.

Results and Discussion

To explore self-regulated learning of secondary school students, descriptive statistics was calculated as whole and on dimensions of Self-Regulation Scale. Details of descriptive statistics are given in following table:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics related to Self-regulated learning of secondary school students

Dimensions of Self-Regulated Learning	Mean	S.D.	Md(Q2)	Mode	Range	Min	Max	Q1	Q3	Q4
Self-Awareness	23.97	5.42	23	20	21	14	35	20	29	35
Planning and Goal Setting	17.38	4.43	17	19	18	10	28	13.75	20	28
Self-Motivation	23.65	4.52	24	28	19	14	33	20	27	33
Self-Control	26.56	5.64	26	26	30	11	41	23	30	41
Self-Evaluation	28.58	5.91	28	22	22	19	41	23.75	32.3	41
Self-Modification	25.02	7.09	26	26	25	12	37	18	30.3	37
Self-Regulated Learning (Total)	145.2	28.1	146.5	156	112	92	204	124	161	204

Table 1 reveals that secondary school students got mean score on self-regulation individual as 145.2 which shows moderate level of self-regulation. Value of mean and median are close but mode is slightly higher which shows that few students are on extreme high side on self-regulation. Students got highest mean score on self-evaluation and lowest mean score on planning and goal

setting. It can be interpreted that students are good evaluator of their learning process but they are not certain about their study goals and planning. However, they are average on all the dimensions.

H₁: There is no significant difference between the self-regulation of girls and boys students studying in secondary classes.

Table 2: Mean Standard Deviation & t-value of self-regulation of boys and girls students

Groups	Value on self-regulation			Degree of freedom	t-value	Level of significance
	N	Mean	S.D.			
Boys	60	143.2	21.24	118	0.77	Not Significant
Girls	60	147.15	13.00			

*0.05 = 1.98 **0.01 = 2.63

After data calculation researcher show it above table-2. Researcher found that value of calculated - t is 0.77, it is lower than table t-value 1.98 at degree of freedom 118 and level of significance 0.05. It is clear that difference between means of both groups is not significant at 0.05 level. So, hypothesis H₁ is accepted for research. On the basis girls and boys of means scores are mostly similar in Self-Regulated Learning. So, we can say that gender is not effect on Self-regulated learning.

H₂: There is no significant impact of self-regulation on academic achievement of secondary school students.

Table 3: F-value of Academic achievement of High, Average and Lower self-regulated learners

Groups	N	Sum	Average	Variance
High Self Regulated Learners	36	2321	64.47	14.88
Average Self Regulated Learners	43	2630	61.16	4.28
Low Self Regulated Learners	41	2107	51.39	22.99

Source of Variation	SS	Df	MS	F
Between Groups	3649.37	2	1824.68	131.73
Within Groups	1620.58	117	13.85	
Total	5269.96	119		

The table 3 show that calculated F-value is 131.73 which is higher than table F-value 4.78 at degree of freedom (2,117) and level of significance 0.01. According to among groups means is significant difference at 0.01 level. So, the related hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, it may be concluded that there is significant difference among high, average scorer lower self-regulated learners on academic achievement of secondary school students. The results showed that the self-regulation learning has an impact on academic achievement of secondary school students.

Here, ANOVA test shows that groups have significant difference in academic achievement, but this significant F value does not pinpoint exactly where the differences exist. For this purpose, t-test is calculated between all combinations of groups one by one.

Table 4: Mean, SD & t-value of academic achievement of high, average and low self-regulated learners

SN	Groups	Academic Achievement			D f	t-value	Level of significance
		N	Mean	S.D.			
1	High Self-Regulated Learners	36	64.47	3.86	51	4.62	Significant at 0.01 level
	Average Self-Regulated Learners	43	61.16	2.07			
2	Average Self-Regulated Learners	43	61.16	2.07	54	12.03	Significant at 0.01 level
	Low Self-Regulated Learners	41	51.39	4.8			
3	High Self-Regulated Learners	36	64.47	3.86	74	13.25	Significant at 0.01 level
	Low Self-Regulated Learners	41	51.39	4.8			

The table 4 unveils that calculated t-value between all the groups is higher than table t-value. Hence, the difference between means is significant at 0.01 level. Therefore, it may be concluded that there is significant impact of self-regulation on academic achievement of secondary school students. High self-regulated learners got high scores on academic achievement and low self-regulated learners have low academic achievement.

Findings of The Study

1. The girls and boys students studying in secondary classes did not have difference on self-regulation learning.

2. Level of Self regulated learning is average/moderate in secondary school students.

3. Self regulated learning has an effect on academic achievement of secondary school students.

4. High scorer on Self Regulated Learning is higher than Average scorer on Self regulated Learning in educational achievement.

5. Average scorer on Self Regulated Learning is higher than Low scorer on Self regulated Learning in educational achievement.

6. High scorer on Self Regulated Learning is higher than Low scorer on Self regulated learning in academic achievement.

Discussion of Findings

Self-regulation has important role in our life. It helps in development of life-long learning skills. Findings showed that the academic skill elements were almost related to the self-regulation elements. In explaining this, it can be said that students who use more self-regulated learning will perform good in their academics. On the basis of this results researcher found that self-regulation is perform a importance to improve academics skills. Researcher should be advised teacher, administration and parents to pay consideration to learner's information and learning. If learners get skilled in self-awareness, self-monitoring and planning of their education, their academic achievement will be higher definitely.

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